

Evaluation of foliar insecticides to control rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* in the field

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Few field trials have been attempted for pesticidal control of the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* because of the tendency of this aquatic insect to be unevenly distributed. The problem was overcome at IRRI by hand-infesting small plots (2 m²) with known numbers of larvae (4 second-instar larvae/hill) from a greenhouse colony.

Eleven insecticides were compared as foliar sprays at 0.75 kg a.i./ha in a volume of 300 liters/ha at 15 days after transplanting. Each plot was encircled with plastic sheeting to prevent interplot larval movement. After infestation, caseworm larvae were allowed to settle for 1 day before spraying. The treatments were rated 10 days later by scoring leaf damage — percent tillers with cut leaves — on the basis of the larval feeding habit of cutting off leaf tips. Because of the behavior of the aquatic larvae, the effects of three sites of application: 1) the plants alone, 2) the paddy water alone, and 3) both plants and water were also compared. The aquatic larvae float inside their cases on the paddy water during the day and return to the rice plants at night. Farmers often irrigate series of fields along a slope. That causes the lower lying fields to receive water from above. Thus, larvae could move from a higher field into a lower, adjacent field that had recently been sprayed. In such a case only the plants would have insecticide residue.

Fresh larvae from the greenhouse colony (10 second-instar larvae/mylar tube cage pushed into the mud around a hill of rice, 1 cage/replication) were used in 3 experiments established after the field plots were sprayed:

1. Rice hills and surrounding water directly caged in the field plots (sprayed plants and paddy water),
2. Rice hills removed from the sprayed field plots, placed in pots in the greenhouse, and immersed in fresh water (sprayed plants only), and
3. In the greenhouse, unsprayed potted rice hills immersed in plastic basins of paddy water which had been set in the field before insecticide application (sprayed paddy water only).

The effect of the insecticides in the 3 experiments was measured as larval mortality 48 hours after infestation by all insecticides tested (Table 1). MTMC was significantly less effective, however, than the 10 other insecticides at 0.75 kg a.i./ha. Lower dosages should be tested in future trials.

The supplementary studies on larval mortality support the conclusion that rice caseworm larvae are highly sensitive to insecticides (Table 2). When larvae were exposed to both sprayed plants and paddy water in the field mortality was high (85-100%) after 48 h. Mortalities were significantly lower with some indicated equal effect from insecticides (MTMC, endosulfan, phosphamidon) when only the plants were sprayed or only the water was sprayed (MTMC, carbaryl, phosphamidon). Mortality means over all insecticides indicated equal effect from spraying either plants or paddy water.

Table 1. Effect of foliar insecticides in reducing plant damage from rice caseworm larvae. IRRI, 1980.

Insecticide ^{a/}	Tillers with cut leaves (%) at ^{b/}	
	1 day before spraying	10 days after spraying
Azinphos ethyl 40 EC	7.3a	1.9a
Triazophos 40 EC	8.4a	2.3a
Malathion 57 EC	7.9a	2.4a
MIPC 50 WP	9.0a	2.5a
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	9.2a	2.6a
Carbaryl 85 WP	8.0a	2.6a
Endosulfan 35 EC	8.0a	2.8a
BPMC 50 WP	8.8a	2.8a
Phosphamidon 50 EC	7.8a	3.2a
Diazinon 20 EC	10.5a	3.4a
MTMC 50 WP	7.6a	6.8b
Untreated	7.8a	16.6c

^{a/} Av of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. Hand-infested with 10 second-instar larvae/hill the day before spraying. EC =emulsifiable concentrate, WP =wetable powder.

^{b/} 0.75 kg a.i./ha, 15 days after transplanting.

Table 2. Effects on caseworm larval mortality of foliar insecticides applied to rice plants, paddy water, or both. IRRI, 1980.

Insecticide ^{a/}	Larval mortality (%) 48 h after spraying of ^{b/}		
	Plants and paddy water ^{c/}	Plants only ^{c/}	Paddy water only ^{d/}
MIPC 50 WP	100 a	100 a	100 a
Diazinon 20 EC	100 a	97 ab	100 a
Azinphos-ethyl 40 EC	100 a	90 ab	100 a
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	100 a	97 ab	95 ab
BPMC 50 WP	100 a	92 ab	95 ab
Malathion 57 EC	100 a	92 ab	85 ab
Carbaryl 85 WP	100 a	95 ab	75 bc
Endosulfan 35 EC	100 a	68 c	85 ab
Phosphamidon 50 EC	95 a	82 bc	80 bc
MTMC 50 WP	85 a	63 c	55 c
Mean	98	88	88
^{a/} 0.75 kg a.i./ha. WP = wettable powder, EC = emulsifiable concentrate.			
Applied 15 days after transplanting.			
^{b/} Corrected using Abbott's formula. 10 second-instar larvae per replication (one cage). In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.			
^{c/} Av, 4 replications.			
^{d/} Av, 2 replications			